

DEVELOPING AN ASPHALT PAVEMENT CRACK DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION MODEL BY USING BEAMLET TRANSFORM ALGORITHM

Hassan Idow Mohamed¹, Assist. Prof. Dr. Mustafa ALAS, PhD².

Near East University, faculty of Civil Engineering Department, Nicosia, North Cyprus ¹

E-mail ¹: hassanidka@gmail.com, E-mail ²: mustafa.alas@neu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Pavement cracking, a prevalent form of road damage, significantly impacts road infrastructure performance and longevity. To address this issue, this paper used MATLAB software to process pavement crack images using the beamlet algorithm. Beamlet transform algorithm for the development of an asphalt pavement crack detection and classification model. the comprehensive crack detection and classification model is employed to categorize various cracks and assess the detection confidence. Subsequently, a dedicated crack segmentation network is deployed for precise segmentation of pavement cracks. The approach includes advancements leading to enhanced precision in crack classification and segmentation. the based on the segmentation results, for perform computations to ascertain the length linear cracks and the area for alligator cracks. the research results show that block crack, alligator crack, transverse crack, and longitudinal crack can all be recognized with outstanding accuracy. Alligator cracks and block cracks have detection rates of 81%, with detection rates for longitudinal and transverse cracks of up to 93%.

Keyword: Pavement Crack, Crack Classification, Beamlet Algorithm, Transform, Longitudinal Crack, Alligator Crack, Block Crack, Transverse crack

1. INTRODUCTION

Pavement cracks represent one of the most important issues in road maintenance, significantly affecting the structural integrity and service life of the road. These cracks, being the preliminary signs of various types of pavement diseases, are capable of inducing potential structural damages to the pavement, thus requiring early identification and timely repair [1, 2]. The current traditional methods of crack detection, while efficient to a certain extent, are marred by their inherent time-consuming nature, labor-intensive characteristics, and lack of accuracy, urging a necessity for more advanced methods for crack detection [3-5].

In response to this need, recent years have seen a proliferation of scientific research aimed at leveraging modern technological advancements to achieve accurate and efficient extraction of crack information from images [6-8]. Numerous techniques for detecting pavement cracks have been published in the literature, including the valley bottom boundary extraction approach [9] and the Prim minimal spanning tree-based crack connection algorithm [10]. However, in changing circumstances, these conventional procedures, which were created expressly for particular databases or scenarios, may not deliver satisfactory results.

Due to advancements in artificial intelligence, deep learning techniques are becoming increasingly frequently applied in the field of pavement crack detection [11–14]. Although these techniques have significantly increased the effectiveness and accuracy of pavement crack detection [15, 16], a number of issues still exist, such as the dependence on complex feature extraction methods, the inability to adapt to different image sources or road sections, the impact of environmental factors on the stability and accuracy of algorithms, and the inability of current

models to directly access road conditions.

The current study proposes a novel strategy based on the combination of deep Beamlet transform Algorithm for pavement crack recognition in order to address these drawbacks, with the aim of offering a general solution that can be applied in various crack detection circumstances. The simultaneous fracture detection and segmentation provided by this approach is a special benefit that boosts model effectiveness [1–5].

The increasing concerns surrounding pavement distresses underscore the importance of developing sophisticated image processing algorithms to facilitate pavement crack inspection. As such, this study also presents a comprehensive review of past studies that have contributed to the field, including but not limited to the use of moment invariant and neural networks [1], the application of histogram projection [2], and the use of neural networks for crack detection and classification [3, 4, 5].

2. METHOD

Beamlet transform can be used to identify images based on pavement crack features; the fundamental procedure is depicted in Fig: 1 and Classification standard of Beamlet transform Algorithm.

3. ALGORITHM FLOWCHART

Fig:1 Algorithm Flowchart

This article utilizes images procured from cement and asphalt roads, accessible at <https://github.com/cuilimeng/CrackForest-dataset>. conducted a quantitative analysis of 1000 images worth of data. Generally, images of pavement cracks display linear attributes and are often discontinuous due to considerable environmental interference, making it challenging for traditional pixel-based methods to effectively detect and categorize these cracks. However, the Beamlet algorithm proves robust in its line detection capabilities, making it suitable for asphalt pavement crack detection and classification tasks.

When asphalt pavement crack detection images are extracted, the crack is projected in both horizontal and vertical planes, which simplifies measuring. A fracture can be classified based on

how many branches it has and its angle in the horizontal direction. According to Table 1, there are four main categories of cracks: block cracks, alligator cracks, longitudinal cracks, and transverse cracks. Each crack's angle is computed from its starting point to its finishing position. Regardless of its angle, a block crack is recognized if a branch is present. The length of the block crack is defined as the greatest value of the Beamlet transform in each cell block of a asphalt pavement crack Detection images, and the sum of the lengths of each block along a crack represents the total length of the cracks.

Table 1. The characteristics of various crack types

Crack types	Crack angle Ω	Branch
Longitudinal	$\Omega \geq 60^\circ$	no
Transverse	$\Omega \leq 30^\circ$	no
Alligator	$60^\circ > \Omega > 30^\circ$	no
Block	-	yes

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Asphalt pavement crack detection image was treated using the steps of image enhancement, segmented image, thresholding, eliminated denoising processing, and image improvement according to the algorithm flow (fig. 4). The results are displayed below. The results of processing the Beamlet algorithm on the various types of pavement crack images are shown in the following figures.

Table 2. block crack classification

Number	Crack angle Ω	Crack length	Crack types
1	10°	0.65127 m	Block

The original crack image from Fig. 2 Block cracks was handled using image enhancement, segmented image thresholding, and removal of denoising processing, yielding a successful denoising outcome. The original image's crack information was very well preserved and can be used to distinguish cracks.

Fig:3 Longitudinal

Table 3. longitudinal crack classification

Number	Crack angle Ω	Crack length	Crack types
1	7°	0.61304 m	Longitudinal

After image processing, Fig. 3 only exhibits one longitudinal crack. The noise in the original image was successfully eliminated, and a distinct fracture edge was produced. to evaluate the

suggested beamlet algorithm's success rate. The statistical findings of crack classification are shown in Table 3 shows the results. To get the success rate, divide the total number of cracks by the number of cracks that were correctly classified. Both a vertical and a horizontal crack may be seen in Figure 3. The crack angle of number 1 is 7° , less than 60° , and is regarded as a longitudinal crack.

Fig:4 Transverse

Table 4. Transverse crack classification

Number	Crack angle Ω	Crack length	Crack types
1	7°	0.58902 m	Transverse

Fig. 4 includes one transverse crack and one long crack. The original Asphalt Pavement Crack image was processed utilizing image enhancement, segmented image thresholding, and removal of denoising processing in order to provide a respectable denoising result. The original image's fracture information was very well preserved and may be used to distinguish between two types of cracks. Number 1's crack angle is 7° , which is less than 30° , and is considered to be a transverse crack.

Fig:5 Alligator

Table 5. Alligator crack classification

Number	Crack angle Ω	Crack length	Crack types
1	10°	1.2484 m	Alligator

Alligator Crack, shown in Fig. 5, has four branches. Alligator crack can be clearly identified in the original image depending on whether a branch is present or absent. And it is clear that the technique can identify the true weak edge while being impervious to noise interference.

The classification of the pavement crack images as longitudinal, transverse, block, and alligator using the images shows the accuracy of the Beamlet algorithm.

Table 6. Success rate of crack classification

Cracks	Number	Block	Longitudinal	Transverse	Alligator
Block	250	213	230		87
Longitudinal	250			238	
Transverse	250			128	
Alligator	250		162		218
Success rate		81%	93%	95%	84%

5. CONCLUSION

The pavement crack images in this research are classified into four sorts using a Beamlet

transform-based method: block, alligator, longitudinal, and transverse types. Images showed that the suggested strategy is quite successful even when noise is present in asphalt pavement crack detection. On noisy pavement images, it may be used to classify various crack types with a high rate of asphalt pavement crack detection and a very low rate of false asphalt pavement crack detection. The Beamlet transform cannot, however, be used to detect problems with a vast area, such as potholes, because it is employed to extract linear features. Additionally, more thorough testing is required to improve the algorithm's usability for spotting different kinds of cracks. Additionally, the cracks' length can be determined using the suggested method, but not their width.

6. RECOMMENDATION

The algorithm has shown promising results in classifying crack types with a high detection rate and low false detection rate, even in the presence of noise. However, to improve its practical applicability, the expanding the algorithm's capabilities, incorporating alternative image processing techniques, and conducting comprehensive testing using diverse datasets, the accuracy and usability of the method can be enhanced, ultimately contributing to more effective pavement maintenance and infrastructure management practices.

7. REFERENCE

- [1] D. Zhang and Q. Li, "Overview of the development of highway pavement rapid detection technology," *Surveying and Mapping Geographic Information*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2015.
- [2] D. Zhang and Q. Li, "Overview of rapid detection technology development of highway pavement," *Mapping Geographic Information*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2015.
- [3] B. Menghe, "Research on the development of expressway in China," *Northern Economy*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 60-61, 2013.
- [4] Ministry of Transport of the People's Republic of China, "2017 statistical bulletin on the development of highway and waterway transportation industry," 2018, http://www.gov.cn/xinwen/2018-03/30/content_5278569.html, 2018-03-30.
- [5] J. Y. Cao, *Research on the Technology of Automatic Pavement Crack Detection Based on Digital Image Processing*, Chang'an University, Xian, China, 2014.
- [6] Z. Liu and Y. Zhang, "Detection technology of damaged road surface based on PDE and wavelet analysis," *Microcomputer and Application*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 35–37, 2012.
- [7] D. An-Guo, L. Miao-Miao, S. O. Science et al., "Crack detection algorithm based on gray correlation," *Application Research of Computers*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 3120-3121, 2013.
- [8] H. Oliveira and P. L. Correia, "Crack-IT an image processing toolbox for crack detection and characterization," in *Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, pp. 798–802, Paris, France, October 2014.
- [9] W. Wang and L. Wu, "Pavement crack extraction based on fractional integral valley bottom boundary detection," *Journal of South China University of Technology (Natural Science Edition)*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 117–122, 2014.
- [10] L. Ren, X. U. Zhigang, X. Zhao et al., "Pavement crack connection algorithm based on Prim minimum spanning tree," *Computer Engineering*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 31–36, 2015.
- [11] Z. Anjun, X. Yang, L. Jia et al., "SRAD-CNN for adaptive synthetic aperture radar image

- classification,” *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 1–25, 2018.
- [12] S. Zhou, Y. Liang, J. Wan et al., “Facial expression recognition based on multi-scale CNNs,” in *Proceedings of the Chinese Conference on Biometric Recognition*, October 2016.
- [13] Z. Zeng, W. Xie, Y. Zhang, and Y. Lu, “RIC-unet: an improved neural network based on Unet for nuclei segmentation in histology images,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 21420–21428, 2019.
- [14] Y.-J. Cha, W. Choi, and O. Büyükoztürk, “Deep learning-based crack damage detection using convolutional neural networks,” *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 361–378, 2017.
- [15] G. Xu, J. Ma, F. Liu, and X. Niu, “Automatic recognition of pavement surface crack based on BP neural network,” in *Proceedings of the 2008 International Conference on Computer & Electrical Engineering*, pp. 19–22, Phuket, Thailand, December 2008.
- [16] Q. Zou, Z. Zhang, Q. Li et al., “DeepCrack: learning hierarchical convolutional features for crack detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 1498–1512, 2018.
- [17] W. R. L. D. Silva and D. S. d. Lucena, “Concrete cracks detection based on deep learning image classification,” *Proceedings*, vol. 2, no. 8, p. 489, 2018.
- [18] L. Zhang, F. Yang, Y. D. Zhang, and Y. J. Zhu, “Road crack detection using deep convolutional neural network,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing*, pp. 3708–3712, IEEE, Phoenix, AZ, USA, September 2016.
- [19] S. Zhao and H. Ning, “Detection of pavement cracks based on convolutional neural network,” *Sensors and Microsystems*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 135–138, 2017.
- [20] M. Eisenbach, R. Stricker, D. Seichter et al., “How to get pavement distress detection ready for deep learning? a systematic approach,” in *Proceedings of the 2017 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Anchorage, AK, USA, May 2017.
- [21] R. Stricker, M. Eisenbach, M. Sesselmann, K. Debes, and H.-M. Gross, “Improving visual road condition assessment by extensive experiments on the extended gaps dataset,” in *Proceedings of the 2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Budapest, Hungary, July 2019.
- [22] H. Nhat-Duc, N. Quoc-Lam, and T. B. Dieu, “Image processing-based classification of asphalt pavement cracks using support vector machine optimized by artificial bee colony,” *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, vol. 32, no. 5, Article ID 04018037, 2018.
- [24] Z. Sun, L. Pei, W. Li, H. Xueli, and C. Yao, “Pavement encapsulation crack detection method based on improved Faster R-CNN,” *Journal of South China University of Technology (Natural Science Edition)*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 84–93, 2020.
- [25] S. Wang, X. Wu, Y. Zhang et al., “Full convolution network image crack detection based on deep learning,” *Journal of Computer Aided Design and Graphics*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 115–123, 2018.
- [26] Zhang, D., & Li, Q. (2015). Overview of the development of highway pavement rapid detection technology. *Surveying and Mapping Geographic Information*, 40(1), 1-8.
- [27] Zhang, D., & Li, Q. (2015). Overview of rapid detection technology development of highway pavement. *Mapping Geographic Information*, 40(1), 1-8.
- [28] Menghe, B. (2013). Research on the development of expressway in China. *Northern Economy*, 7(3), 60-61.

- [29] Ministry of Transport of the People's Republic of China. (2018). 2017 statistical bulletin on the development of highway and waterway transportation industry. Retrieved from http://www.gov.cn/xinwen/2018-03/30/content_5278569.html.
- [30] Cao, J. Y. (2014). Research on the Technology of Automatic Pavement Crack Detection Based on Digital Image Processing. Chang'an University, Xian, China.
- [31] Liu, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2012). Detection technology of damaged road surface based on PDE and wavelet analysis. *Microcomputer and Application*, 31(8), 35-37.
- [32] An-Guo, D., Miao-Miao, L., O. Science, et al. (2013). Crack detection algorithm based on gray correlation. *Application Research of Computers*, 30(10), 3120-3121.
- [33] Oliveira, H., & Correia, P. L. (2014). Crack-IT an image processing toolbox for crack detection and characterization. In *Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)* (pp. 798-802), Paris, France.